

Supplementary materials for the paper ‘Exploring the Effects of Virtual Agents’ Smiles on Human-Agent Interaction: A Mixed-Methods Study’ by Torre et al. published at ACII 2021

I. AGENT’S SCRIPTED QUESTIONS

The virtual therapist asked 10 questions to the participants:

- 1) I’m Fred! Nice to meet you. What brings you in today?
- 2) What do you hope to get out of today?
- 3) What specific goal do you have?
- 4) How important is this goal for you?
- 5) What would be the benefits of achieving this goal?
- 6) Have you already taken any steps towards achieving this goal?
- 7) What is realistic for you to achieve this goal?
- 8) How confident do you feel about your ability to make changes?
- 9) Was there a previous occasion where you set a goal and were successful?
- 10) Based on what we’ve discussed, would it be okay if I suggested a few next actions that you could take? I will read out a list of ten possible next actions that you could take, and then you will tell me what you think.

II. SCRIPTED POSSIBLE NEXT ACTIONS

Here are the 10 possible next actions that the virtual therapist listed to the participants:

- Use the stairs instead of the lift
- Park further away when you go grocery shopping
- Take a walk at lunch
- Take a free dance class at lunch time
- Walk around the office during breaks
- Have a fruit instead of candy as a snack
- Try not to eat after 8 pm
- Install an app for sleep quality monitoring
- Have a full glass of water next to you at all times
- Do some stretching during breaks